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Re.Nature Cities

Experimental and numerical methods to assess the role of stReet trees as a Nature-Based Solution for climate change adaptation of Cities

WORK PACKAGE WP4 – Experimental assessment of street trees as urban NBS

DELIVERABLE D4.3. – Drag Coefficient Database

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Re.Nature Cities: Deliverable 3.4: Drag Coefficients Database

1. Introduction

This study has been conducted within the framework of the research project “Re.Nature Cities” that aims to evaluate via experimental and simulation means the ability of street trees as nature-based solution (NBS), to act as an effective measure against the consequences of climate change on the built environment. Despite the undeniable effect of urban greenery on the regulation of the outdoor thermal environment (Reis and Lopes, 2019), street trees also impact urban ventilation as they act as barriers, disturbing the wind flow and affecting buildings’ energy needs, thermal comfort and air quality. The positive effect of wind sheltering during the cold winter period, can be significantly counterbalanced during the warmer periods of the year, with the existing evidence revealing that the green elements’ implementation in the built environment without holistically account all the vegetation-air-buildings interactions, can even exacerbate human discomfort and deteriorate indoor natural ventilation (Zheng et al., 2020). It becomes thus obvious that the accurate evaluation of the street trees’ effect as a NBS towards the resilience of the built environment would impose a precise determination of the heat and mass exchange between the vegetation elements and the environment, strongly correlated with trees’ aerodynamical, geometrical and thermal properties.

2. Experimental Set-up

2.1. Definition of C_d measurements

One of the main objectives of this experimental work was to determine the drag coefficient (C_d) of natural trees/shrubs with different geometric properties (height, H_{tree} and width, W_{tree}) and porosities. The natural trees/shrubs selected for the experimental study are representative Mediterranean deciduous and evergreen species i.e. *i*) Clementine, *ii*) Magnolia, *iii*) Oleander and *iv*) Tilia . The aerodynamic forces were measured for these four different trees for the same velocity range. For repeatability and sensitivity analysis purposes, three different samples of each tree/shrub were tested at two different orientations (0° and 90°) with respect to the direction of the wind flow. The drag coefficient C_d of the tree species, for a given reference wind speed U_{ref} (m/s) is given as:

$$C_d = \frac{2F}{\rho U_{ref}^2 A_{frontal}} \quad (2.1)$$

where F is the measured drag force (N) in the direction of the wind speed, ρ is air density (kg/m^3) and $A_{frontal}$ is the projected frontal area (m^2). The calculation of the projected frontal area $A_{frontal}$ was based on an image processing workflow of the photographs taken

before drag force measurements, when the trees/shrubs were at rest. The step-by-step analysis will be presented in the Image processing work flow section (Section 2.2). The three-dimensional forces acting on each tree sample were measured simultaneously using a three-dimensional load cell (Kistler, multi-component force plate, Type 9253B) with a sampling frequency, f_s , of 100 Hz for an acquisition time, t_{ac} , of 120 sec. The mean load force acting in the flow direction (F_x) was used in Eq. 2.1. The effect of the incoming wind speed was tested for ten reference velocities U_{ref} (m/s), in the range from 1.4 m/s to 10 m/s, with a step of 1 m/s. The reference velocity, U_{ref} , was measured directly from a Prandtl pitot tube, placed on the wind tunnel ceiling (see Figure 1), upstream of the trees based on dynamic pressure, as:

$$U_{ref} = \sqrt{\frac{2P_{dyn}}{\rho}} \quad (2.2)$$

while the air density, ρ was calculated based on barometric pressure, relative humidity and temperature measurements, recorded simultaneously with the force measurements, according to the formula :

$$\rho = \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{B}{R_o} - \phi p_w \left(\frac{1}{R_o} - \frac{1}{R_w} \right) \right) \quad (2.3)$$

where B is the barometric pressure (Pa), T is the absolute temperature (K), ϕ is the relative humidity (range between 0 and 1), R_o is the gas constant of dry air (287.05 J/kg K), R_w is the gas constant of water vapour (461.5 J/kg K) and p_w is the vapour pressure (Pa). p_w is given as:

$$p_w = 0.0000205e^{0.0631846T} \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 1: Wind tunnel set-up of the drag force and hotwire measurements.

2.2. Image processing work flow

A digital image is an array which describes the value of pixels. Three types of images are discussed, ranging from simple to complex : *i*) binary, *ii*) gray-scale and *iii*) color. A binary

image is also known as black and white. Here, each pixel will be either a one i.e. white or a zero i.e. black, making it a simple method of storing masks and divisions of pixels into two classes. One step higher in complexity is a gray-scale image. A gray-scale image states for each pixel where its value is on a scale ranging from black i.e. 0 to white i.e. 255. This allows for a resolution of 2^8 colors. Finally, the most complex image, is a colored image with usually represented with RGB-channels (Red Blue Green). Here each pixel has three values ranging from 0 to 255 describing the presence of red, green and blue in the image respectively, leading to a possibility of 2^{24} colors. In our case, for the calculation of frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ the gray-scale type image was adopted while for the calculation of optical and aerodynamic porosities, the binary type.

The calculation of the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$, was based on an image processing workflow of the photographs taken before drag force measurements, when the trees/shrubs were at rest. The original image was captured as shown in Figure 2a and a white background was added (see Figure 2b). This allowed us to distinguish the area of the object, i.e. tree, from the noisy background, i.e. the wind tunnel floor, the lights etc. Then a gray-scale image was used as you can see in Figure 2c, and thresholding was adopted to classify tree and non-tree pixels. Thresholding is a single-channel binarisation method, that makes it possible to set a specific value (i.e. a boundary) and assign values below or above it, to one class or another. After thresholding, the image was inverted (see Figure 2d) and the perimeter was required to determine the enclosed frontal area. The perimeter was determined by identifying all pixels that enclose a large shape in the binary image (inverted image). These pixels are found by placing an agent on the binarised image and letting it walk around the positive class until it reaches its starting point again. It then returns the coordinates of the points if the number of points is above a threshold value. If the number of points is below a threshold, this means that the shape it has encircled, is most likely, not the most important shape in the image and it will try again. Thus, the surface area for the enclosed frontal area of the crown in red contour was determined, ignoring the empty spaces among leaves in the crown (see Figure 2f). Prior to this, initial calculations of frontal area, were based on the determination of the area of the *Convex hull* (see Figure 2e). Particularly, a convex object is an object with no interior angles greater than 180° . The tested trees/shrubs can be characterized as convex objects (see Figure 3a-e). Hull is referred to the exterior or the shape of the object. Therefore, the *Convex hull* of a shape or a group of points is a tight fitting convex boundary around the points or the shape. The area of convex hull is presented in Figure 2e. The projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ was then calculated based on the enclosed surface area below intense white contour. Figure 2 incorporates a step-by-step image analysis work flow as it has already been described.

Once the tree is binarised, the frontal area, $A_{frontal}$, is extracted in the form of pixels². To find a more physical representation of the surface area, the number of pixels is converted to m². To do this, the geometric properties of each tested tree/shrub are recorded: the height (H_{tree}) and the width (H_{tree}) of all tested samples. So if someone knows the height and width in pixels from the image analysis and the height and width in the real dimension (m), then the transformation from pixels to m can be easily extracted. Therefore, it was decided to perform a sensitivity analysis to calculate the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$, based on the convex hull area (see Figure 2e) and/or the exact perimeter of the crown in red contour (see Figure 2f), considering once the height dimension and then the width dimension for the pixel area conversion. The final results of this sensitivity analysis and their effects on the drag coefficients for the entire velocity range are shown in Figure 5a-d.

Figure 2: Step by step an example of the post processing analysis and calculation of the frontal images of the natural tree Magnolia (Sample 1, 0° orientation) at rest : (a) Original image, (b) Original image with white background, (c) Original image at grayscale, (d) Inverted image, (e) Frontal area in white contour and (f) Frontal area in red contour.

Figure 3: Selected frontal thresholded images of natural trees captured at rest: a) Oleander (Sample 1, 0°), b) Magnolia (Sample 1, 0°), c) Clementine (Sample 1, 0°), d) Clementine (Sample 2, 0°) and e) Tilia (Sample 1, 0°). The red region indicates the calculated frontal area of the tree, $A_{frontal}$.

2.3. Calculations of optical porosity, β_p and aerodynamic porosity, α_p

The aerodynamic porosity, α_p is defined (Guan et al., 2003) as the ratio of the time average velocity behind the obstacle (U_b) and the average wind speed of the approaching flow:

$$\alpha_p = \frac{\int_{A_{frontal}} U_b(x, y) A_{frontal}}{\int_{A_{frontal}} U_{ref}(x, y) A_{frontal}} \quad (2.5)$$

where $A_{frontal}$ is the projected frontal area of the obstacle. The aerodynamic porosity determines the proportion of the flow that passes through the porous material with respect to the flow that diverges from the obstacle. Despite the fact that this aerodynamic parameter was originally introduced to characterize windbreaks, recent studies (Manickathan et al., 2018; Fellini et al., 2022) have adopted aerodynamic porosity for individual trees. In our

experimental study, however, the direct calculation of the aerodynamic porosity was not possible, but only indirectly via the calculation of the optical porosity, β_p .

Optical porosity, β_p , is defined as the ratio between the open surface area of a porous material and its total surface area (Fellini et al., 2022). Furthermore, the optical porosity is defined by Kenney (1987) as the ratio between the number of white pixels to the total number of pixels within the silhouette of the tree. The silhouette area is considered as the projected frontal area of the tree, $A_{frontal}$, as already analyzed in Section 2.2 and its values are presented in Table 1.

Guan et al. (2003) has introduced an empirical relationship between the aerodynamic porosity, α_p and the optical porosity, β_p , obtained from a wind tunnel drag study of realistic tree-like windbreak models, and expressed as follows :

$$\alpha_p = \beta_p^{n=0.4} \quad (2.6)$$

Fellini et al. (2022) has calculated the aerodynamic porosity, α_p in both ways in her recent study: on the basis of Eq. 2.3 by performing velocity measurements upstream and downstream of a single tree exposed to a homogeneous approaching flow profile, but also by using Eq. 2.3 by processing digital images. She concluded that the exponent n calculated by the values α_p and β_p is equal to $n \sim 0.402$, which is consistent with the work of Guan et al. (2003). It is extracted that the aerodynamic porosity, α_p , based on Eq. 2.3, can be calculated correctly, even if the velocity measurements are not always possible to perform.

Table 1: Specifications of the species, samples, geometric characteristics of the trees (H_{trees} , W_{trees} , $A_{frontal}^*$), optical porosities, β_p and aerodynamic porosities, α_p .

Species	No Sample	Orientation	H_{trees} (m) W_{trees} (m)	$A_{frontal}$ (m ²)	Blockage ratio (%)	β_p	α_p
Clementine	1	0°	1.30 - 1.43	0.77	8.8	0.0280	0.2391
Clementine	1	90°	1.29 - 1.26	0.68	7.8	0.0413	0.2796
Clementine	2	0°	1.42 - 1.34	0.80	9.1	0.0391	0.2735
Clementine	2	90°	1.38 - 1.38	0.88	10.1	0.0435	0.2854
Clementine	3	0°	1.60 - 1.10	0.98	11.2	0.0262	0.2331
Clementine	3	90°	1.45 - 1.10	0.80	9.1	0.0131	0.1767
Magnolia	1	0°	1.52 - 0.72	0.43	4.9	0.0827	0.3690
Magnolia	1	90°	1.56 - 0.83	0.51	5.8	0.1158	0.4221
Magnolia	2	0°	1.60 - 0.90	0.57	6.5	0.0374	0.2687
Magnolia	2	90°	1.55 - 0.87	0.57	6.5	0.0470	0.2943
Magnolia	3	0°	1.57 - 0.70	0.53	6.1	0.0286	0.2413
Magnolia	3	90°	1.61 - 0.72	0.55	6.3	0.0476	0.2959
Oleander	1	0°	0.90 - 0.87	0.28	3.2	0.1519	0.4706
Oleander	1	90°	0.90 - 0.65	0.27	3.1	0.0996	0.3974
Oleander	2	0°	1.10 - 0.68	0.40	4.6	0.1220	0.4311
Oleander	2	90°	1.07 - 0.94	0.35	4.0	0.2129	0.5386
Oleander	3	0°	0.98 - 0.58	0.21	2.4	0.0644	0.3338
Oleander	3	90°	0.92 - 0.60	0.21	2.4	0.1339	0.4474
Tilia	1	0°	2.09 - 1.12	0.54	6.2	0.0664	0.3380
Tilia	1	90°	2.29 - 1.15	0.63	7.2	0.0846	0.3724
Tilia	2	0°	2.31 - 0.61	0.36	4.1	0.0540	0.3112
Tilia	2	90°	2.30 - 0.80	0.44	5.0	0.2082	0.5338
Tilia	3	0°	2.02 - 0.84	0.27	3.1	0.0099	0.1581
Tilia	3	90°	2.03 - 1.07	0.29	3.3	0.0888	0.3796

* $A_{frontal}$ has been calculated based in the red contour area and the tree height as a way to transform pixel to m.

2.4. Inlet profiles

Prior to the drag force measurements, hotwire measurements were performed in the large test section (H: 2.5m × W: 3.5m × L: 12m) of the closed-loop wind tunnel at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), without trees. The instantaneous streamwise velocity was measured at 13 points along a vertical line above the center of the wind tunnel floor, without a tree model in the test section. A single hotwire sensor was used, operating in a constant temperature mode (Constant Temperature Anemometry, CTA). The velocity signal was sampled at 10 kHz for a total measurement time of 154 s. The reference velocity was equal to $U_{ref} = 5.73$ m/s and measurements were taken at the center and lateral positions ($\pm 0.16W$, at the tree crown edges) to ensure that all trees were exposed to a nearly uniform wind speed profile. Two main flow characteristics were determined: the non-dimensional mean streamwise velocity and the mean streamwise turbulence intensity profiles along the wind tunnel height. Both profiles are shown in Figure 4a-b. The upstream turbulence level is low, with maximum values up to 1.5%. The choice of an almost uniform wind profile instead of an atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) was based on the fact that despite different tree heights, all tested samples are exposed to similar velocity and turbulence profiles and the comparison between the measurements would be meaningful.

Figure 4: Inlet vertical profiles at $x = 0.4L$ ($L = 12\text{m}$), without trees : (a) normalized mean streamwise velocity profile U/U_{ref} and (b) mean streamwise turbulence intensity TI_u , in the center (black line, position A), and in the lateral positions (red line, position B) and (green line, position C).

3. Results

3.1. Results of C_d measurements based on different definitions of frontal area : a sensitivity analysis

Figure 5a-d shows the mean drag coefficient, C_d , as a function of the mean wind speed U (m/s) for the four species tested: *i*) Clementine, *ii*) Magnolia, *iii*) Oleander and *iv*) Tilia. Error bars in Figures 5a-d include sample and orientation variations. As already analyzed in Section 2.2, the differences between the four diagrams are based on the determination of projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$, (Figure 5a-b in white contour and Figure 5c-d in red contour) and on the conversion of the pixel area (Figure 5a, 5c taking into account the height dimension and Figure 5b, 5d the width dimension respectively).

A general observation is that the values of the drag coefficient decrease with increasing speed, regardless of the calculation of the frontal area and the conversion of the pixel area. However, one can observe the wide spread of the drag coefficient values for a given wind speed, ranging from 0.25 to 0.95 for the four species. In particular, the total drag coefficient values in Figure 5c are higher than those in Figure 5a, and this is directly related to the calculation of the frontal area. Overestimating the convex hull area of the tree decreases the corresponding drag coefficient value according to Eq. 2.1, where $A_{frontal}$ is the denominator. Here, the conversion from pixels to m is the same for both diagrams and is based on the dimension of the tree height, H_{tree} . The same result can be derived from the comparison of Figure 5b, 5d with the tree width, W_{tree} .

In addition, the comparison between Figure 5a-b and Figure 5c-d shows the effect of the pixel area conversion on the calculation of the frontal area and thus on the drag coefficient. Both combinations (Figure 5a-b and Figure 5c-d) show that the width dimension only has a major influence on Magnolia (red line), while the other three curves follow the same qualitative and quantitative trend. This can be easily explained by comparing the geometric properties of the Magnolia samples in Table 1. It can be seen that the height of Magnolia is almost twice as large as its width and therefore has a remarkable effect on the final calculation of the drag coefficient. For all other species, the analogy between height and width is almost 1:1, which justifies the small variations for Clementine, Oleander and Tilia. A recent experimental study conducted by Zheng et al. (2020) shows that tree height is the most important geometric parameter, while crown width and height as well as breast diameter are related to tree height. Therefore, we conclude that the calculation of the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ in red contour and the conversion of the pixel area based on the tree height corresponds to the most representative calculation of the drag coefficient, as shown in Figure 5c.

In Figure 5c, the values of the drag coefficient for a given wind speed, are between 0.55 and 0.95 for the four species. These values are within the range measured for other tree species, according to Vollsinger et al. (2005) and Manickathan et al. (2018). The mean trend for all species is that, at low velocities (≤ 5 m/s) the C_d values increase with increasing velocity until they reach a maximum value and then decrease sharply as the velocity further increases. This is probably related to the high foliage of the trees and the reconfiguration of the tree, as also observed in Manickathan et al. (2018). According to Vogel (1989), the reconfiguration occurs at higher wind speeds, causing a decay of the drag coefficient. To further understand the influence of reconfiguration, the relationship of drag force with wind speed is investigated in Section 3.3.

a) Frontal area (in white contour)
pixel to m : based on H_{tree} dimension

b) Frontal area (in white contour)
pixel to m : based on W_{tree} dimension

c) Frontal area (in red contour)
pixel to m : based on H_{tree} dimension

d) Frontal area (in red contour)
pixel to m : based on W_{tree} dimension

Figure 5: Estimates of the mean drag coefficient, C_d [-] as a function of mean wind speed, U , m/s for clementine (blue), magnolia (red), oleander (yellow) and tilia (purple) trees. a) The frontal area in white contour with pixel to meter transformation based on the height tree dimension (H_{tree}), b) the frontal area in white contour with pixel to meter transformation based on the width tree dimension (W_{tree}), c) the frontal area in red contour with pixel to meter transformation based on the height tree dimension (H_{tree}) and d) the frontal area in red contour with pixel to meter transformation based on the width tree dimension (W_{tree}). Error bars represent the standard deviation values of C_d .

3.2. Effects of porosity

Recent studies (Guan et al., 2003; Manickathan et al., 2018) have investigated the role of porosity - aerodynamic, optical and volumetric - on the drag coefficient values, C_d , for a given Reynolds number range. The same tendency can be observed in all these studies: the

drag coefficient values increase to a certain degree at low aerodynamic porosity and then decrease as the aerodynamic porosity becomes higher. This tendency is also evident in our wind tunnel studies and can be observed in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Drag coefficient C_d as a function of aerodynamic porosity, α for Re.Nature data and literature data as extracted by Manickathan et al. (2018) study.

The graph shows the drag coefficient values as a function of aerodynamic porosity for four different Reynolds numbers between $9E+04$ and $1.59E+05$ for selected tested species, to be compatible with previous studies. The calculation of the Reynolds number was based on the tree height dimension. All recorded values are given in Table 2. It is interesting to note that among the tested species and the calculated aerodynamic porosities, there is one case where the aerodynamic porosity is 0.315, which is close to the critical value. An interesting conclusion is that when the aerodynamic porosity is doubled, i.e. at a value ≥ 0.3 , the drag coefficient drops to 50 %. However, the Reynolds number seems to be an indecisive factor, as a similar increase in its value leads to a drag coefficient change of less than 3.5 %. According to Dong et al. (2007), the critical value for aerodynamic porosity is 0.3. The author explains that there is a critical porosity above or below which the airflow characteristics differ strongly. In particular, when the porosity value is below the critical porosity, the air flows over the porous medium, while when the porosity is higher than 0.3, the bleed flow, i.e. the air passing through the porous medium and not over it, prevails and the bleed flow balances the reversed flow. This choice of flow regime influences the velocity fields downstream of the porous medium, in our case the tree, and leads to strong reversed flows and thus to a reduction in the shelter distance.

Table 2: Drag coefficient (C_d) and aerodynamic porosity (α_p) values, for $Re_{H_{tree}}$ range between $9E+04$ and $1.59E+05$, of selected tested species.

Re.Nature			
Species	$Re_{H_{tree}}$	C_d	α_p
Oleander	$9E+04$	0.553	0.436
Clementine	$1.35E+05$	0.879	0.248
Magnolia	$1.48E+05$	0.872	0.315
Oleander	$1.59E+05$	0.573	0.436

3.3. Effects of reconfiguration

Aero- and hydrodynamic loadings are among the most important abiotic stress factors to which plants are exposed. To overcome them, plants rely on their flexibility to change their shape and reduce their resistance when exposed to fluid flow (Gosselin, 2019). Vogel (1984) introduced the term "reconfiguration" to express the change in shape of trees/plants when exposed to a fluid flow. The leaves and branches of the trees are twisted and bent so that the tree crowns reduce the frontal area normal to the flow and become more streamlined. According to Eq. 2.1, the drag force is proportional to the square of the wind speed for moderate and high Reynolds numbers, which is generally accepted for bluff bodies. However, Vogel (1989) has expressed the above equation in a more general form that includes the properties of a porous body, namely as:

$$F \propto U^{2+E} \quad (3.1)$$

where F is the drag force (N), U (m/s) is the incoming wind speed, and E is the Vogel exponent (-). If the leaves were rigid, the Vogel exponent, E would be zero and the Eq. 3.3 would be identical to the equation for the drag force of bluff bodies (see Eq. 2.1). The same author (Vogel, 1984, 1989) presents the values of the Vogel exponents which vary between 0 and -1.0. The more negative the Vogel exponent, E , the more linear the increase in the drag with the incoming wind speed or the more linear the decrease in the drag force coefficient, C_d with respect to the incoming flow velocity. In the present study, the Vogel exponents were calculated based on a drag coefficient as a function of the mean wind speed plot, as shown in Figure 7a-d, for each tested tree species, i.e. Clementine, Magnolia, Oleander and Tilia. A Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (Gavin, 2019) was used to produce a fit in the form of $C_d = mU^E$. In addition, Table 3 lists the fitted parameters of the Levenberg - Marquardt algorithm, including its standard errors and the corresponding values of the Vogel exponent of selected literature data.

A look at the Figures 7a-d shows that for all tested vegetation species, there is an almost linear range ($U \geq 5.0$ m/s) in which the Vogel exponents are extracted. Their values range between -0.40 and -0.70. These values are in the same range as in the wind tunnel study of Manickathan et al. (2018), i.e. -0.33 and -0.51, in which hardwood (holly) and coniferous (cypress) tree species were tested. A basic similarity between these two wind tunnel studies is the use of small trees in age, but differing in size (i.e. height) by a factor of four (the tested samples in the present study are larger). In the present study, Magnolia and Clementine are the two species which reconfigure the most, the two with higher density foliage. In addition, the age of trees has a significant effect on the lower moment of elasticity according to Watt et al. (2008). The younger trees appear to be more flexible as their branches are still under development and therefore reconfigure more strongly compared to mature trees.

The oak tree investigated in the field study of Bekkers et al. (2022) was a mature tree and the calculated Vogel exponent was equal to $E = -0.26$ (the drag force coefficient and the frontal area were calculated as described in Section 2.1 and Section 2.2. The oak is six and eight times taller and larger than the trees tested in this study, which means that is less vulnerable to higher velocity values.

Figure 7: Estimates of the mean drag coefficient, C_d [-] as a function of the mean wind speed, U , m/s for clementine (blue), magnolia (red), oleander (yellow) and tilia (purple) trees. A Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm is used to produce a fit in the form of $C_d = mU^E$ and is indicated by black dashed lines for $U \geq 5.0$.

Table 3: The values of constant (m) with the calculated standard errors(%) and the values of the Vogel exponent, E and its calculated standard errors (%), for the tested tree/shrub species. Selected Vogel exponent values of literature data (wind tunnel and field measurements).

Re.Nature			Literature		
Species	$m \pm \text{error} (\%)$	$E \pm \text{error} (\%)$	Species	m	E
Clementine	2.21 ± 0.03	-0.60 ± -0.12	holly ¹	[-]	-0.33
Magnolia	3.11 ± 0.47	-0.70 ± -2.13	holly ¹ defoliated	[-]	-0.05
Oleander	1.23 ± 0.23	-0.40 ± -0.71	cypress ¹	[-]	-0.51
Tilia	1.39 ± 0.18	-0.42 ± -0.60	oak ² (A_e)	0.77	-0.26

¹ Manickathan et al. (2018)

² Bekkers et al. (2022)

References

- Bekkers C. C., Angelou N., and Dellwik E. (2022). Drag coefficient and frontal area of a solitary mature tree. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* 220. ISSN: 01676105. DOI: [10.1016/j.jweia.2021.104854](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2021.104854).
- Dong Z., Luo W., Qian G., and Wang H. (Sept. 2007). A wind tunnel simulation of the mean velocity fields behind upright porous fences. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 146.(1-2), 82–93. ISSN: 01681923. DOI: [10.1016/j.agrformet.2007.05.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2007.05.009).
- Fellini S., Marro M., Del Ponte A. V., Barulli M., Soulhac L., Ridolfi L., and Salizzoni P. (2022). High resolution wind-tunnel investigation about the effect of street trees on pollutant concentration and street canyon ventilation. *Building and Environment* 226. ISSN: 03601323. DOI: [10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109763](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109763).
- Gavin H. P. (2019). The Levenberg-Marquardt method for non linear least squares curve-fitting problems. Duke University, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, p. 19. URL: <https://people.duke.edu/~hpgavin/ce281/lm.pdf>.
- Gosselin F. P. (2019). Mechanics of a plant in fluid flow. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 70.(14), 3533–3548. ISSN: 14602431. DOI: [10.1093/jxb/erz288](https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erz288).
- Guan D., Zhang Y., and Zhu T. (2003). A wind-tunnel study of windbreak drag. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 118.(1-2), 75–84. ISSN: 01681923. DOI: [10.1016/S0168-1923\(03\)00069-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1923(03)00069-8).
- Kenney W. A. (1987). A method for estimating windbreak porosity using digitized photographic silhouettes. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 39, 94.
- Manickathan L., Defraeye T., Allegrini J., Derome D., and Carmeliet J. (2018). Comparative study of flow field and drag coefficient of model and small natural trees in a wind tunnel. *Urban Forestry and Urban Greening* 35, 230–239. ISSN: 16108167. DOI: [10.1016/j.ufug.2018.09.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.09.011).
- Reis C. and Lopes A. (2019). Evaluating the cooling potential of urban green spaces to tackle urban climate change in Lisbon. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 11.(9). ISSN: 20711050. DOI: [10.3390/su11092480](https://doi.org/10.3390/su11092480).
- Vogel S. (1984). Drag and Flexibility in Sessile Organisms. *American Zoologist* 24, 37–44. URL: <https://academic.oup.com/icb/article/24/1/37/104436>.
- Vogel S. (1989). Drag and Reconfiguration of Broad Leaves in High Winds. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 40.(217), 941–948. URL: <http://jxb.oxfordjournals.org/>.
- Vollsinger S., Mitchell S. J., Byrne K. E., Novak M. D., and Rudnicki M. (2005). Wind tunnel measurements of crown streamlining and drag relationships for several hardwood species. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 35.(5), 1238–1249. ISSN: 00455067. DOI: [10.1139/x05-051](https://doi.org/10.1139/x05-051).
- Watt M. S., D’Ath R., Leckie A. C., Clinton P. W., Coker G., Davis M. R., Simcock R., Parfitt R. L., Dando J., and Mason E. G. (2008). Modelling the influence of stand structural, edaphic and climatic influences on juvenile *Pinus radiata* fibre length. *Forest Ecology and Management* 254.(2), 166–177. ISSN: 03781127. DOI: [10.1016/j.foreco.2007.07.036](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2007.07.036).
- Zheng S., Guldmann J. M., Liu Z., Zhao L., Wang J., Pan X., and Zhao D. (June 2020). Predicting the influence of subtropical trees on urban wind through wind tunnel tests and numerical simulations. *Sustainable Cities and Society* 57. ISSN: 22106707. DOI: [10.1016/j.scs.2020.102116](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102116).

Re.Nature Cities: Data Documentation

1. Introduction

This document contains the necessary information to understand the performed experiment and to access and use the available data. Section 2 includes a detailed description of the experimental set up while Section 3 describes the data organization.

2. Experimental Set-up

2.1. Inlet profiles

All measurements were conducted in the closed-loop, low-speed boundary layer wind tunnel at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA). This wind tunnel has a test section of: H: 2.5m × W: 3.5m × L: 12m, as shown in Figure 1. The inflow velocity profiles were measured in the large test section of the wind tunnel, without trees. The instantaneous streamwise velocity was measured at 13 points along a vertical line above the center of the wind tunnel floor and measurements were taken at its lateral positions ($\pm 0.16W$, at the tree crown edges, see Figure 1) to ensure that all trees were exposed to a nearly uniform wind speed profile. A single hotwire sensor was used, operating in a constant temperature mode (Constant Temperature Anemometry, CTA). The velocity signal was sampled at 10 kHz for a total measurement time of 154 s. The reference velocity was equal to $U_{ref} = 5.73$ m/s. Two main flow characteristics were determined: the non-dimensional mean streamwise velocity profiles and the mean streamwise turbulence intensity profiles along the wind tunnel height.

2.2. Definition of C_d measurements

One of the main objectives of this experimental work was to determine the drag coefficient (C_d) of natural trees/shrubs with different geometric properties (height, H_{tree} and width, W_{tree}) and porosities. The natural trees/shrubs selected for the experimental study are representative Mediterranean deciduous and evergreen species i.e. *i)* Clementine, *ii)* Magnolia, *iii)* Oleander and *iv)* Tilia . The aerodynamic forces were measured for these four different trees for the same velocity range. For repeatability and sensitivity analysis purposes, three different samples of each tree/shrub were tested at two different orientations (0° and 90°) with respect to the direction of the wind flow. The drag coefficient C_d of the tree species, for a given reference wind speed U_{ref} (m/s) is given as:

$$C_d = \frac{2F}{\rho U_{ref}^2 A_{frontal}} \quad (2.1)$$

where F is the measured drag force (N) in the direction of the wind speed, ρ is air density (kg/m^3) and $A_{frontal}$ is the projected frontal area (m^2). The calculation of the projected

frontal area $A_{frontal}$ was based on an image processing workflow of the photographs taken before drag force measurements, when the trees/shrubs were at rest. The step-by-step analysis is presented in Figure 2a-e. The three-dimensional forces acting on each tree sample were measured simultaneously using a three-dimensional load cell (Kistler, multi-component force plate, Type 9253B) with a sampling frequency, f_s , of 100 Hz for an acquisition time, t_{ac} , of 120 sec. The mean load force acting in the flow direction (F_x) was used in Eq. 2.2. The effect of the incoming wind speed was tested for ten reference velocities U_{ref} (m/s), in the range from 1.4 m/s to 10 m/s, with a step of 1 m/s. The reference velocity, U_{ref} , was measured directly from a Prandtl pitot tube, placed on the wind tunnel ceiling (see Figure 1), while the air density, ρ was calculated based on barometric pressure, relative humidity and temperature measurements, recorded simultaneously with the force measurements.

Figure 1: Wind tunnel set-up of the drag force and hotwire measurements.

The calculation of the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$, was based on an image processing workflow of the photographs taken before drag force measurements, when the trees/shrubs were at rest. The original image was captured as shown in Figure 2a and a white background was added (see Figure 2b). This allowed us to distinguish the area of the object, i.e. tree, from the noisy background, i.e. the wind tunnel floor, the lights etc. Then a gray-scale image was used as you can see in Figure 2c, and thresholding was adopted to classify tree and non-tree pixels. Thresholding is a single-channel binarisation method, that makes it possible to set a specific value (i.e. a boundary) and assign values below or above it, to one class or another. After thresholding, the image was inverted (see Figure 2d) and the perimeter was required to determine the enclosed frontal area. The perimeter was determined by identifying all pixels that enclose a large shape in the binary image (inverted image). Thus, the surface area for the enclosed frontal area of the crown in red contour was determined, ignoring the empty spaces among leaves in the crown (see Figure 2e). Once the tree is binarised, the frontal area, $A_{frontal}$, is extracted in the form of pixels². To find a more physical representation of the surface area, the number of pixels is converted to m²

based on the height (H_{tree}) of all tested samples. Selected frontal thresholded images of natural trees captured at rest can be found in Figure 3a-e.

Figure 2: Step by step an example of the post processing analysis and calculation of the frontal images of the natural tree Magnolia (Sample 1, 0° orientation) at rest : (a) Original image, (b) Original image with white background, (c) Original image at grayscale, (d) Inverted image, (e) Frontal area in red contour.

Figure 3: Selected frontal thresholded images of natural trees captured at rest: a) Oleander (Sample 1, 0°), b) Magnolia (Sample 1, 0°), c) Clementine (Sample 1, 0°), d) Clementine (Sample 2, 0°) and e) Tilia (Sample 1, 0°). The red region indicates the calculated frontal area of the tree, $A_{frontal}$.

2.3. Calculations of optical porosity, β_p and aerodynamic porosity, α_p

Optical porosity, β_p , is defined as the ratio between the open surface area of a porous material and its total surface area (Fellini et al., 2022). Furthermore, the optical porosity is defined by Kenney (1987) as the ratio between the number of white pixels to the total number of pixels within the silhouette of the tree. The silhouette area is considered the projected frontal area of the tree, $A_{frontal}$.

Guan et al. (2003) has introduced an empirical relationship between the aerodynamic porosity, α_p and the optical porosity, β_p , obtained from a wind tunnel drag study of realistic

tree-like windbreak models, and expressed as follows :

$$\alpha_p = \beta_p^{n=0.4} \quad (2.2)$$

It is extracted that the aerodynamic porosity, α_p , based on Eq. 2.3, can be calculated correctly, even if the velocity measurements are not always possible to perform.

2.4. Calculations of Leaf Area Density, (LAD), Total Leaf Area and Leaf Mass per Area (LMA)

3. Data organization

In this section, every subsection describes the contents of each of the available folders.

3.1. Inlet profiles

This folder includes three subfolders:

1. **Position A** : The file Inlet profile (Position A).dat contains the velocity and turbulence intensity profiles in the empty wind tunnel test section in the center, at the location of the tested tree.
2. **Position B** : The file Inlet profile (Position B).dat contains the velocity and turbulence intensity profiles in the empty wind tunnel test section in the lateral position, i.e. $+0.16W$, at the tree crown edge, of the tested tree.
3. **Position C** : The file Inlet profile (Position C).dat contains the velocity and turbulence intensity profiles in the empty wind tunnel test section in the lateral position, i.e. $-0.16W$, at the tree crown edge, of the tested tree.

Provided data include: the height (z , in m) of the 13 measurement points, the corresponding non-dimensional variable z/H , where H is the wind tunnel height ($H = 2.5$ m), the mean streamwise velocity, U (m/s), the non-dimensional mean streamwise velocity U/U_{ref} where U_{ref} is the free wind speed ($U_{ref} = 5.73$ m/s), and the mean streamwise turbulence intensity, TI_u (%).

3.2. Tree species

This folder includes four subfolders:

1. **Clementine**: This folder includes three files :
 - Clementine_drag force.txt : The file contains the 10 mean values of selected variables calculated as the average value of three different Clementine samples in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (Total samples = 6). The first column contains the mean values of the tested reference velocity (Total Mean_U, m/s), the second the standard deviation of the reference velocity (Stdev_U, m/s), the third the mean drag forces (Total Mean_Fd, N), the fourth the standard deviation of the drag forces (Stdev_Fd, N), the fifth the calculated drag force coefficient based on Eq. 2.2 (Total Mean_Cd, [-]) and the sixth column the standard deviation of the calculated drag coefficient (Stdev_Cd, [-]).

- Clementine_frontal area_optical porosity.txt : The file contains the 6 values of the three different Clementine samples (second column) in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (third column), the geometric characteristics per sample and orientation including the tree height, H_{tree} (m), the tree width, W_{tree} (m), the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ (m²) and the optical porosity, β_p . For the projected frontal area, the conversion from pixels to m, is based on the dimension of tree.
- Clementine_LAD_LAI_LMA.txt : The file contains the 3 values of the three different Clementine samples, the geometric characteristics including the crown height, H_{crown} (m), the crown width, W_{crown} (m) per sample, the Leaf Area Density (LAD) [-], the Total Leaf Area (), the Leaf Mass per Area (LMA, g/m²) and the standard deviation of Leaf Mass per Area (Stdev_LMA, g/m²). For Clementine sample 3, the values for LMA and Stdev_LMA are not included.

2. **Magnolia:** This folder includes three files :

- Magnolia_drag force.txt : The file contains the 10 mean values of selected variables calculated as the average value of three different Magnolia samples in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (Total samples = 6). The first column contains the mean values of the tested reference velocity (Total Mean_U, m/s), the second the standard deviation of the reference velocity (Stdev_U, m/s), the third the mean drag forces (Total Mean_Fd, N), the fourth the standard deviation of the drag forces (Stdev_Fd, N), the fifth the calculated drag force coefficient based on Eq. 2.2 (Total Mean_Cd, [-]) and the sixth column the standard deviation of the calculated drag coefficient (Stdev_Cd, [-]).
- Magnolia_frontal area_optical porosity.txt : The file contains the 6 values of the three different Magnolia samples (second column) in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (third column), the geometric characteristics per sample and orientation including the tree height, H_{tree} (m), the tree width, W_{tree} (m), the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ (m²) and the optical porosity, β_p . For the projected frontal area, the conversion from pixels to m, is based on the dimension of tree.
- Magnolia_LAD_LAI_LMA.txt : The file contains the 3 values of the three different Magnolia samples, the geometric characteristics including the crown height, H_{crown} (m), the crown width, W_{crown} (m) per sample, the Leaf Area Density (LAD) [-], the Total Leaf Area (), the Leaf Mass per Area (LMA, g/m²) and the standard deviation of Leaf Mass per Area (Stdev_LMA, g/m²).

3. **Oleander:** This folder includes three files :

- Oleander_drag force.txt : The file contains the 10 mean values of selected variables calculated as the average value of three different Oleander samples in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (Total samples = 6). The first column contains the mean values of the tested reference velocity (Total Mean_U, m/s), the second the standard deviation of the reference velocity (Stdev_U, m/s), the third the mean drag forces (Total Mean_Fd, N), the fourth the standard deviation of the drag forces (Stdev_Fd, N), the fifth the calculated drag force coefficient based on Eq. 2.2 (Total Mean_Cd, [-]) and the sixth column the standard deviation of the calculated drag coefficient (Stdev_Cd, [-]).
- Oleander_frontal area_optical porosity.txt : The file contains the 6 values of the three different Oleander samples (second column) in two different orientations

(0° and 90°) (third column), the geometric characteristics per sample and orientation including the tree height, H_{tree} (m), the tree width, W_{tree} (m), the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ (m²) and the optical porosity, β_p . For the projected frontal area, the conversion from pixels to m, is based on the dimension of tree.

- Oleander_LAD_LAI_LMA.txt : The file contains the 3 values of the three different Oleander samples, the geometric characteristics including the crown height, H_{crown} (m), the crown width, W_{crown} (m) per sample, the Leaf Area Density (LAD) [-], the Total Leaf Area (), the Leaf Mass per Area (LMA, g/m²) and the standard deviation of Leaf Mass per Area (Stdev_LMA, g/m²).

4. **Tilia:** This folder includes three files :

- Tilia_drag force.txt : The file contains the 10 mean values of selected variables calculated as the average value of three different Tilia samples in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (Total samples = 6). The first column contains the mean values of the tested reference velocity (Total Mean_U, m/s), the second the standard deviation of the reference velocity (Stdev_U, m/s), the third the mean drag forces (Total Mean_Fd, N), the fourth the standard deviation of the drag forces (Stdev_Fd, N), the fifth the calculated drag force coefficient based on Eq. 2.2 (Total Mean_Cd, [-]) and the sixth column the standard deviation of the calculated drag coefficient (Stdev_Cd, [-]).
- Tilia_frontal area_optical porosity.txt : The file contains the 6 values of the three different Tilia samples (second column) in two different orientations (0° and 90°) (third column), the geometric characteristics per sample and orientation including the tree height, H_{tree} (m), the tree width, W_{tree} (m), the projected frontal area, $A_{frontal}$ (m²) and the optical porosity, β_p . For the projected frontal area, the conversion from pixels to m, is based on the dimension of tree.
- Tilia_LAD_LAI_LMA.txt : The file contains the 3 values of the three different Tilia samples, the geometric characteristics including the crown height, H_{crown} (m), the crown width, W_{crown} (m) per sample, the Leaf Area Density (LAD) [-], the Total Leaf Area (), the Leaf Mass per Area (LMA, g/m²) and the standard deviation of Leaf Mass per Area (Stdev_LMA, g/m²).

References

- Fellini S., Marro M., Del Ponte A. V., Barulli M., Soulhac L., Ridolfi L., and Salizzoni P. (2022). High resolution wind-tunnel investigation about the effect of street trees on pollutant concentration and street canyon ventilation. *Building and Environment* 226. ISSN: 03601323. DOI: [10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109763](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109763).
- Guan D., Zhang Y., and Zhu T. (2003). A wind-tunnel study of windbreak drag. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 118.(1-2), 75–84. ISSN: 01681923. DOI: [10.1016/S0168-1923\(03\)00069-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1923(03)00069-8).
- Kenney W. A. (1987). A method for estimating windbreak porosity using digitized photographic silhouettes. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 39, 94.